

Synthesis, spectral and antibacterial studies of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) and mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes of antipyrine Schiff bases

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Manuscript received 8 October 2007, accepted 28 November 2007

Abstract : The reactions of mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride and bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride with Schiff bases, derived by condensing 4-aminoantipyrine with benzaldehyde (L_1), furfuraldehyde (L_2), pyridine-4-carboxaldehyde (L_3) or salicylaldehyde (L_4H), have been studied in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran or dichloromethane and products of types $[Cp_2M(L)Cl]Cl$, $[CpTiCl_3(L)]$ ($L = L_1, L_2$ or L_3); $[Cp_2M(L_4)]Cl$, $[CpTiCl_2(L_4)]$, $[CpTi(L_4)_2]Cl$ [$M = Ti^{IV}$ or Zr^{IV}] have been isolated. Tentative structures are proposed for these complexes based upon elemental analyses, electrical conductance and spectral (electronic, IR, 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) data. Attempts have been made to establish a correlation between antibacterial activity and the structures of the products.

Keywords : Titanim(IV), zirconium(IV), antipyrine, antibacterial study.

Introduction

Antipyrine (2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) and its derivatives exhibit a wide variety of potentially useful biological properties¹. A number of workers synthesized and studied the properties of nickel(II) and zinc(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazones derived from 4-formylantipyrine², copper(II) complexes of 4-(2-pyrrolylmethylideneamino)-antipyrine³ and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of 4-(2-pyrrolylmethylideneamino)/4-(2-thienylmethylideneamino)/4-(furfurylideneamino)/4-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)antipyrine⁴. It is reported that pyrazole based ligands display variable coordination behaviour and a variety of coordination possibilities to metal centres. On the other hand, since the discovery of the Ziegler-Natta catalyst for the polymerization of olefins, considerable importance has been attached to the chemistry of organic derivatives of titanium/zirconium due to their increasing applications in the field of homogeneous catalysis and chemical fixation of molecular nitrogen^{5,6}. In addition, a marked tendency of these metals to form complexes of high coordination number has also stimulated interest in the study of their complexes with various ligands.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) derivatives

with Schiff bases derived from 4-aminoantipyrine. The structure of ligands is shown below (1).

R = C_6H_5 (L_1), C_4H_3O (L_2), C_5H_4N (L_3), $C_6H_4(OH)$ (L_4H)
(1)

Results and discussion

A systematic study of the reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride and mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride with Schiff bases in anhydrous THF or CH_2Cl_2 may be represented by the following equations :

Table 1. Reactions of Cp_2MCl_2 ($M = Ti$ or Zr) and $CpTiCl_3$ with antipyrene Schiff base

Reactants (Molar ratio)	Reflux time (h)	Product color, yield(%)	Decomp. temp. °C	Mol. formula (formula weight)	Found (Calcd.) (%)				
					C	H	N	Cl	M
$Cp_2TiCl_2 + L_1$ (1 : 1)	9	$[Cp_2Ti(L_1)Cl]Cl$ red, 68	80	$C_{28}H_{27}N_3OCl_2Ti$ (540.3)	62.0 (62.2)	4.9 (5.0)	7.6 (7.8)	13.0 (13.1)	8.7 (8.9)
$Cp_2ZrCl_2 + L_1$ (1 : 1)	7	$[Cp_2Zr(L_1)Cl]Cl$ yellow brown, 68	132	$C_{28}H_{27}N_3OCl_2Zr$ (583.7)	57.3 (57.6)	4.5 (4.7)	7.0 (7.2)	12.1 (12.1)	15.4 (15.6)
$Cp_2TiCl_2 + L_2$ (1 : 1)	9	$[Cp_2Ti(L_2)Cl]Cl$ reddish brown, 70	112	$C_{26}H_{25}N_3O_2Cl_2Ti$ (530.3)	58.6 (58.9)	4.7 (4.8)	7.4 (7.9)	13.2 (13.4)	9.0 (9.0)
$Cp_2ZrCl_2 + L_2$ (1 : 1)	9	$[Cp_2Zr(L_2)Cl]Cl$ light brown, 62	141	$C_{26}H_{25}N_3O_2ZrCl_2$ (573.6)	54.2 (54.4)	4.2 (4.4)	7.1 (7.3)	12.3 (12.4)	15.7 (15.9)
$Cp_2TiCl_2 + L_3$ (1 : 1)	10	$[Cp_2Ti(L_3)Cl]Cl$ dark brown, 68	120	$C_{27}H_{26}N_4OCl_2Ti$ (541.3)	59.6 (59.9)	4.5 (4.8)	10.0 (10.3)	13.0 (13.1)	8.6 (8.8)
$Cp_2ZrCl_2 + L_3$ (1 : 1)	10	$[Cp_2Ti(L_3)Cl]Cl$ brown, 65	160	$C_{27}H_{26}N_4OCl_2Zr$ (584.6)	55.0 (55.5)	4.2 (4.5)	9.4 (9.6)	12.0 (12.1)	15.5 (15.6)
$Cp_2TiCl_2 + L_4H$ (1 : 1 : 1)	10	$[Cp_2Ti(L_4)]Cl$ red brown, 74	100	$C_{28}H_{26}N_3O_2ClTi$ (519.9)	64.5 (64.7)	4.8 (5.0)	7.9 (8.0)	6.6 (6.8)	9.1 (9.2)
$Cp_2ZrCl_2 + L_4H$ (1 : 1)	10	$[Cp_2Zr(L_4)]Cl$ pink brown, 72	111	$C_{28}H_{26}N_3O_2ClZr$ (563.2)	59.4 (59.7)	4.5 (4.7)	7.3 (7.5)	6.1 (6.3)	16.1 (16.2)
$CpTiCl_3 + L_1$ (1 : 1)	18	$[CpTiCl_3(L_1)]$ brown, 64	142	$C_{23}H_{22}N_3OCl_3Ti$ (510.7)	54.0 (54.1)	4.2 (4.3)	8.2 (8.2)	20.7 (20.8)	9.2 (9.2)
$CpTiCl_3 + L_1$ (1 : 1)	12	$[CpTiCl_3(L_2)]$ dark brown, 62	207	$C_{21}H_{20}N_3O_2Cl_3Ti$ (500.6)	50.1 (50.4)	3.8 (4.0)	8.1 (8.4)	21.0 (21.2)	9.6 (9.6)
$CpTiCl_3 + L_3$ (1 : 1)	15	$[CpTiCl_3(L_3)]$ brown, 65	182	$C_{22}H_{21}N_4OCl_3Ti$ (511.7)	51.3 (51.6)	4.0 (4.1)	10.7 (10.9)	20.7 (20.8)	9.3 (9.4)
$CpTiCl_3 + L_4H$ (1 : 1)	12	$[CpTiCl_2(L_4)]$ dark brown, 68	217	$C_{23}H_{21}N_3O_2Cl_2Ti$ (490.2)	56.1 (56.4)	4.1 (4.3)	8.2 (8.6)	14.3 (14.5)	9.7 (9.8)
$CpTiCl_3 + L_4H$ (1 : 2)	12	$[CpTi(L_4)_2]Cl$ chocolate brown, 74	210	$C_{41}H_{37}N_6O_4ClTi$ (761.1)	64.4 (64.7)	4.7 (4.9)	10.8 (11.0)	4.5 (4.7)	6.2 (6.3)

L_1 = Schiff base derived from benzaldehyde and 4-aminoantipyrene; L_2 = Schiff base derived from furfuraldehyde and 4-aminoantipyrene;

L_3 = Schiff base derived from pyridine-4-carboxyaldehyde and 4-aminoantipyrene; L_4 = Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 4-aminoantipyrene.

Colors and elemental analyses are listed in Table 1. The complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide, nitrobenzene and tetrahydrofuran. The molar conductances of the complexes except $[Cp_2M(L)Cl]Cl$ and $[Cp_2M(L_4)]Cl$ in nitrobenzene are in the range 5–12.0 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ which are well below the range observed for uni-univalent electrolytes in this solvent. The molar conductances of the complexes of type $[Cp_2M(L)Cl]Cl$ and $[Cp_2M(L_4)]Cl$ indicate their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The visible spectra of the complexes show a broad band in the 22800–23000 cm^{-1} region which can be assigned to charge-transfer, a result in accord with their $(n-1)d^{0ns^0}$ electronic configuration.

The IR spectral bands most useful for determining the Schiff base's mode of coordination are given in Table 2. The $\nu(C=O)$ absorption shifts, at *ca.* 1650 cm^{-1} in the free ligands, to lower ($\sim 25 cm^{-1}$) wave numbers in the titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) complexes indicates the

involvement of the antipyrene oxygen in chelation^{3,4}. The $\nu(M-O)$ band appears⁷ at *ca.* 465 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(C=N)$ shift to the Schiff base from *ca.* 1610 cm^{-1} to lower energy ($\sim 20 cm^{-1}$) in the spectra of complex indicated^{8,9} the involvement of the azomethine-N in chelation. The far IR spectra of complexes display band at *ca.* 440 cm^{-1} due⁹ to $\nu(M-N)$. The broad band at 3380 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of L_4H is assigned to hydrogen bonded OH. Furthermore, the existence of a broad weak band at 1910 cm^{-1} can be taken as an evidence for the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the type $O-H \cdots N$. This is also supported³ by the appearance of the $\nu(C-O)$ phenolic band at 1260 cm^{-1} . Upon complexation, the bands at 3380 and 1910 cm^{-1} disappeared and that at 1260 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1290 cm^{-1} , indicating the bonding of the ionized phenolic oxygen to titanium(IV) or zirconium(IV). The $\nu(M-O)$ band appears¹⁰ at *ca.* 500–480 cm^{-1} in the far IR spectra of the complexes with ligand L_4H .

The pyridine ring vibrations, which are most affected

Table 2. Important IR spectral bands (cm⁻¹)

Complex	v(C=O)	v(C=N)	v(C-O)	v(M-O) phenolic	v(M-O) ketonic	v(M-N)	C ₄ H ₅ ring
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₁)Cl]Cl	1630s	1590m	1290s	500s	470m	445m	3000w, 1420m, 1020m, 800w
[Cp ₂ Zr(L ₁)Cl]Cl	1625s	1580m	1290s	480s	465m	440m	2990w, 1415m, 1025m, 810w
[Cp ₂ TiCl ₃ (L ₁)]	1628s	1585m	1295s	495s	470m	445m	3010w, 1410w, 1020m, 810w
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₂)Cl]Cl	1635s	1595m	1290s	490s	465m	440m	3000w, 1425w, 1010m, 800w
[Cp ₂ Zr(L ₂)Cl]Cl	1630s	1590m	1280s	480s	460m	430m	3010w, 1420m, 1030w, 820w
[CpTiCl ₃ (L ₂)]	1635s	1592m	1285s	480s	462m	428m	2995w, 1415m, 1020w, 815w
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₃)Cl]Cl	1630s	1585m	1290s	495s	470m	445m	3000w, 1420w, 1020w, 815w
[Cp ₂ Zr(L ₃)Cl]Cl	1625s	1580m	1285s	485s	460m	440m	3010w, 1415w, 1015w, 810w
[CpTiCl ₃ (L ₃)]	1630s	1585m	1288s	500s	465m	440m	3000w, 1415w, 1015w, 800w
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₄)Cl]	1630s	1590m	1295s	495s	468m	450m	2990w, 1420m, 1010w, 820w
[Cp ₂ Zi(L ₄)Cl]	1622s	1580m	1290s	480s	460m	440m	3010w, 1415m, 1020w, 800w
[CpTiCl ₂ (L ₄)]	1625s	1585m	1295s	500s	465m	445m	3015w, 1410m, 1018w, 810w
[CpTi(L ₄) ₂]Cl	1625s	1590m	1290s	495s	462m	450m	3000w, 1420w, 1020w, 815w

by the pyridine nitrogen coordination to the metal atom, are the pyridine ring deformation, in-plane ring deformation and out-of-plane ring deformation. These weak vibrations appear at 1540, 720 and 500 cm⁻¹, respectively in the ligand derived from pyridine-4-carboxaldehyde (L₃). However, in its complexes, these bands remain unaffected indicating the non-participation of the pyridine nitrogen in coordination.

Absorption bands occurring at *ca.* 3000 cm⁻¹ for v(C-H), *ca.* 1420 cm⁻¹ for v(C-C), *ca.* 1025 cm⁻¹ for v(C-H) and 810 cm⁻¹ for δ(C-H) in all the complexes are assigned to the cyclopentadienyl group and indicate that these groups are π-bonded to the metal.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes have been recorded (Table 3) in deuterated

dimethylsulphoxide. The line intensities were determined by planimetric integration. A comparison of the ligands with the complexes leads to the following conclusion :

- The δ 6.60–6.82 signal may be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl ring protons and indicate the rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis.
- The singlet at *ca.* δ 9.2 is assigned to the azomethine proton.
- The methyl protons at C-5 and N-1 are observed as singlets at δ 2.45 and δ 3.10 respectively.
- The spectrum of ligand L₄H shows weak singlet at *ca.* 10.82, which can be assigned, to the hydrogen bonded -OH. This signal disappears in its corresponding complexes.

Table 3. NMR data (δ, ppm) of titanium(IV) derivatives with antipyrine Schiff bases

Complex	¹ H				¹³ C			
	η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅ ring	H C=N	CH ₃ -C(5)	CH ₃ -N(1)	Phenyl	η ⁵ -C ₄ H ₅	-C=O	H-C=N
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₁)Cl]Cl	6 70s	9 25s	2 48s	3 12s	7 60–7 78m	117 0	171 5	146 8
[Cp ₂ Zr(L ₁)Cl]Cl	6 75s	9 28s	2 50s	3 14s	7 62–7 80m	116 5	168 2	144 2
[CpTiCl ₃ (L ₁)]	6 72s	9 26s	2 46s	3 10s	7 50–7 75m	117 8	172 8	145 7
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₂)Cl]Cl	6 60s	9 20s	2 42s	3 12s	7 65–7 70m	117 5	170 5	148 2
[Cp ₂ Zi(L ₂)Cl]Cl	6 65s	9 24s	2 45s	3 15s	7 68–7 75m	116 8	167 2	149 6
[CpTiCl ₃ (L ₂)]	6 60s	9 20s	2 40s	3 12s	7 65–7 72m	117 2	171 6	140 5
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₃)Cl]Cl	6 68s	9 25s	2 42s	3 10s	7 55–7 65m	117 6	170 2	146 8
[Cp ₂ Zi(L ₃)Cl]Cl	6 72s	9 28s	2 46s	3 15s	7 58–7 62m	116 4	169 8	141 6
[CpTiCl ₃ (L ₃)]	6 70s	9 26s	2 42s	3 12s	7 52–7 62m	117 2	174 2	144 5
[Cp ₂ Ti(L ₄)Cl]	6 75s	9 22s	2 40s	3 10s	7 50–7 62m	117 5	173 6	146 2
[Cp ₂ Zr(L ₄)Cl]	6 80s	9 25s	2 45s	3 14s	7 55–7 64m	116 2	168 8	140 2
[CpTiCl ₂ (L ₄)]	6 78s	9 20s	2 42s	3 12s	7 48–7 60m	117 8	170 4	146 8
[CpTi(L ₄) ₂]Cl	6 75s	9 24s	2 45s	3 10s	7 52–7 62m	117 5	172 2	145 5

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of antipyrene Schiff bases and their corresponding titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibitor zone (mm)	
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
L_1	6	7
$[Cp_2Ti(L_1)Cl]Cl$	18	14
$[Cp_2Zr(L_1)Cl]Cl$	12	10
$[CpTiCl_3(L_1)]$	22	20
L_2	8	8
$[Cp_2Ti(L_2)Cl]Cl$	16	15
$[Cp_2Zr(L_2)Cl]Cl$	12	9
$[CpTiCl_3(L_2)]$	20	22
L_3	12	12
$[Cp_2Ti(L_3)Cl]Cl$	20	18
$[Cp_2Zr(L_3)Cl]Cl$	14	12
$[CpTiCl_3(L_3)]$	22	20
L_4H	10	8
$[Cp_2Ti(L_4)Cl]Cl$	16	15
$[Cp_2Zr(L_4)Cl]Cl$	14	12
$[CpTiCl_2(L_4)]$	22	20
$[CpTi(L_4)_2]Cl$	18	17

^{13}C NMR spectra : The ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligands and their corresponding complexes were recorded (Table 3) in DMSO. The ^{13}C resonance signals are assigned according to chemical shift theory. The compounds show cyclopentadienyl peak at *ca.* δ 116 (relative to TMS). A considerable shift in the position of C=O (*ca.* 160 ppm in the ligands) and CH=N (*ca.* 135 ppm in the ligands) support the coordination through azomethine and keto groups. The signals due to C-CH₃ and N-CH₃ appear at *ca.* δ 12.10 and δ 35.0, respectively.

Antibacterial activity : The antibacterial activity of the complexes together with the parent ligands has been screened against Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* by the paper disk plate method at 1000 ppm conc. The inhibition zone (mm) around each disk was measured after 24 h and the results of these studies are listed in Table 4. The results lead to the following conclusions :

- The complexes are slightly more toxic than the parent ligands.
- The titanium complexes show better activity than zirconium complexes.
- Mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives possess better activity than bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives.
- Mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivative

containing 1 mole of ligand $[CpTiCl_2(L_4)]$ shows better activity than compounds containing 2 moles of ligand $[CpTi(L_4)_2]Cl$.

Accordingly, the major factors affecting the activity of complexes are the structure of the complex and the electronic state of the metal ion. In mono(cyclopentadienyl)-titanium(IV) complexes, the metal center is more exposed structurally as compared to the bis(cyclopentadienyl) complexes. Such exposures facilitates the attachment of substrates to the metal center and increases biological activity³. Similarly, in mono(cyclopentadienyl)-bis-ligand complex, the metal center is sterically less exposed to substrate as compared to mono-ligand complex and therefore, later complex shows better activity.

(2)

(3)

(4)

(5)

(6)

On the basis of elemental analyses, electrical conductance and spectral data, the following structures are proposed for $[\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{L})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ (**2**), $[\text{CpTiCl}_3(\text{L})]$ (**3**), $(\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{L}_4))\text{Cl}$ (**4**), $[\text{CpTiCl}_2(\text{L}_4)]$ (**5**) and $[\text{CpTi}(\text{L}_4)_2]\text{Cl}$ (**6**) complexes.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. THF was dried by heating under reflux over Na wire. The Et_3N was purified by published method¹¹. Mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride was prepared¹² from CpTiCl_2 and TiCl_4 in *p*-xylene. Bis-(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride was prepared¹³ by heating CpNa with appropriate metal chloride in N_2 atmosphere. Elemental analyses and physical measurements were made as reported earlier¹⁴. The Schiff bases, were prepared as reported earlier⁴.

Reactions of Cp_2MCl_2 and CpTiCl_3 with Schiff base (L_1 , L_2 or L_3) :

To a solution of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride or mono(cyclopentadienyl)-titanium(IV) trichloride (20 mmol) in dry THF (*ca.* 30 cm^3) was added the appropriate Schiff base (20 mmol). The resulting clear mixture was refluxed for *ca.* 7–18 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to *ca.* 15 cm^3 under reduced pressure. Light petroleum (b.p. 60–80 °C) (10 cm^3) was then added. The colored precipitate so obtained was thoroughly washed with Et_2O and recrystallized from THF : Et_2O (1 : 1).

Reaction of Cp_2MCl_2 with Schiff base, L_4H :

Schiff base (L_4H) (20 mmol) was added to a solution of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride (10 mmol) in dry THF (~40 cm^3). To this triethylamine (20 mmol) was added and the mixture stirred for 10 h at room temperature. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The colored product was crystallized from a THF : pet. ether (60–80 °C) mixture (1 : 1).

Reactions of CpTiCl_3 with Schiff base, L_4H :

The mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives were prepared by mixing CpTiCl_3 (20 mmol) with the ligand L_4H in appropriate molar ratios (20 mmol or 40

mmol) and adding about 50 cm^3 of dichloromethane followed by refluxing for 12 h. The solutions were then filtered and volume reduced to about 10 cm^3 . Addition of dry pet. ether (60–80 °C, 15 cm^3) to the above solution and allowed to stand overnight gave yellow to brown crystals which were filtered and dried *in vacuo*.

The details of the reactions and important physical characteristics, analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

MKM and CMT thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi and University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of JRF and project fellowship, respectively.

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